

FROM NERVES TO KNOWLEDGE: CLASS ROOM ANXIETY AMONG NURSING STUDENTS AT NURSING INSTITUTES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Anxiety is an emotionally adaptive reaction to unclear or frightening situations that helps people act and react appropriately. Nursing students have frequently reported feeling anxious for a variety of reasons, such as the challenging nature of nursing courses and non-cooperative behavior of nursing faculty.

Objectives: The objective of the study was to evaluate the level of class room anxiety among nursing students.

Methodology: A descriptive cross sectional study design was used to assess the level of class room anxiety among nursing students at public and private colleges of nursing in Karachi, Pakistan from November, 2023 to January, 2024, sample size was calculated by using Open Epi version 3.0 and total 140 participants were responded while convenient sampling technique was used. A well-structured questionnaire, the Situational Communication Apprehension Measure, developed by Richmond, served as the model for the instrument used in this study to collect the data. The data was analyzed by using SPSS version 26.0. The participants of the study were the students of Generic BS Nursing above the age of 18 to 32 years while all the students of other nursing discipline were excluded from the study.

Results: 20.72% of participants indicated normal range of anxiety, 28.57% shown mild to moderate level of anxiety, 42.86% reported severe degree of anxiety, and 7.85% experienced extreme degree of anxiety.

Conclusion: Anxiety levels among nursing students in the classroom range from moderate to severe, Larger-scale research is still required, and interventional studies must be carried out in the future.

Keywords: Knowledge, Class Room Anxiety, Nursing Students, Nursing Institutes

Introduction

Higher education is an important aspect of life, and in the current educational system, assessments and exams have a big influence on students' future job choices (1). Officially speaking, anxiety is defined as an adverse emotional state that includes a person's subjective sensations of tension, apprehension, and uneasiness along with the autonomic nervous system being activated (2). In addition, previously changes in our routine, such as working via the internet, temporary joblessness, virtual schooling and shortage of interaction. Students' academic performance may suffer as a result of this growing concern (3). Anxiety is an emotionally adaptive reaction to unclear or frightening situations that helps people act and react appropriately (4). Maintaining both the quantity and quality of a healthy existence is crucial for nurses in order to fulfill their primary purpose in life (5). The literature recognizes the possible impact of anxiety on learning and performance and discusses it in great detail for nursing students participating in a variety of clinical settings (6). The physical environment and personnel instruction for healthcare workers, including nurses and nursing students, is known as a clinical placement (7). Nursing students have frequently reported feeling anxious for a variety of reasons, such as the challenging nature of nursing courses, worry about test results, a sense that there is not enough faculty support, and occasionally even clinical teacher nervousness (8). Nursing students engage in activities that include observation, imitation, continuous assessment, investigation, practical application, and reflective processes in order to enhance their nursing abilities (9). Like all students, nursing students under intense pressure to fulfill academic and practical requirements. This pressure is increased by the fear that even small errors could have catastrophic repercussions for patients and their careers; teachers have observed that test anxiety is higher in nursing students than in other areas (10). Workload, student conduct, and employment conditions all predict anxiety and perceived stress levels; the biggest factor causing anxiety to increase is the severe lack of administrative support (11). While anxiety could be helpful for some jobs, it can also be detrimental to learning. Typically, stress and anxiety are normal experiences for nursing students during their training and study(12). Teaching nursing skills through distance education has been observed to induce significant anxiety in the majority of students (13). Wang L et al., highlights the detrimental effects of unresolved stress and anxiety on the mental health of nursing students, which has prompted a focused effort to develop psychological therapies for stress reduction during clinical practice over the past 20 years (14). According to a recent multicenter study conducted in Spain with 28,559 students from 16 universities, 20.84% of them had significant exam anxiety and needed professional help. Furthermore, compared to students pursuing other university degrees, research on participants enrolled in healthcare degree programs shows a higher prevalence of pre-exam anxiety, ranging from 30% to 50% (15). In order to meet the rigorous standards of a nursing education, nursing students must overcome a variety of obstacles during their learning process. Nursing students may experience higher levels of stress and anxiety when they struggle with these issues compared to students in other disciplines (16). The study aim to understand the level of anxiety among nursing students the finding of this study will ultimately useful in order to develop targeted interventions and support systems and, eventually, enhance the learning process and overall wellbeing of nursing students as they progress through their education and training, a full understanding of this kind of anxiety is necessary.

Methodology

A cross sectional descriptive quantitative study designed was used, the sample size was calculated via an open epi with 95% confidence interval, a population of 250, and the calculated sample size was 152, 12 out of total participants did not respond to the questionnaire, the study was conducted

in public sector and private colleges of nursing, inclusion criteria for the participants was all students enrolled for bachelors of science in nursing (1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, 4th year) male and female, aged between 18 to 32 years .all other nursing students counting post RN, registered nurses were excluded from the study. The Situational Communication Apprehension Measure, developed by Richmond, served as the model for the instrument used in this study. Its predicted alpha reliability is approximately 0.90. Participants are given a form with statements on it that express how they feel about the classroom. They were instructed to encircle the 5 points Likert scale, (1) “strongly disagree” and (5) “strongly agree”, In particular, questions with bold text are recorded backwards, and the total Classroom Anxiety score is obtained by summing the results of each item. The entire scores ranging from 20 to 100, 20 - 44 indicate the normal level of anxiety, score of 45-59 indicate the mild to moderate level of anxiety, 60-74 indicate sever level of anxiety and more than 75 indicate extremely severe level of anxiety. The data analyzed by using SPSS version 26, and frequency percentages was used to clarify the demographic data. The anxiety levels in the classroom were also represented using frequency and percentage measures. Convenient sampling technique was used to approach the participants. The duration of the study from November, 2023 to January 2024, data was gathered from the participants after the approval from concerned authorities (PINS/2023/131 and IRC/DC/113/23) to maintain the ethical consideration written informed consent was taken from the participants and verbal explanation of the objectives, anonymity and confidentiality was well explained to the participants.

Results

Table 1 illustrates the results of demographic variables, including age, gender, year of education, and place of residence of the study participants. Among all the participants, 45% (n=63) was between the ages of 18 and 22. With a gender distribution of 64.28% (n=90), women make up the majority of participants. About the participants' year of education, 57.14% (n=80) are in their first year, and 15.71% (n=22) are in their second year. Third-year students make up 17.86% (n=25), while fourth-year students make up 9.29% (n=13). 57.14% (n=80) of the total study participants live in hostels, making up the bulk of the population.

Table 1 Demographic Characteristic n=140

Variables	N	%
Age		
18-22	63	45%
23-27	45	32.14%
28-32	32	22.86%
Gender		
Male	50	35.72%
Female	90	64.28%
Year of Education		
First year	80	57.14%
Second year	22	15.71%
Third year	25	17.86%
Fourth year	13	9.29%
Participant's Place or residence		
With family	50	35.72%
In a hostel	80	57.14%
With relatives	10	7.14%

Table 2 shows the degree of anxiety in the classroom. To be more precise, 20.72% (n = 29) of participants indicated normal range of anxiety, 28.57% (n = 40) shown mild to moderate level of anxiety, 42.86% (n = 60) reported severe degree of anxiety, and 7.85% (n = 11) experienced extreme degree of anxiety.

Table 2 Degree of Classroom Anxiety

Degree of class Room Anxiety	N	%
Normal range of anxiety	29	20.72
Mild to moderate degree of anxiety	40	28.57
Severe degree of anxiety	60	42.86
Extreme degree of anxiety	11	7.85

Discussion

In the discussion section the result of current study was compared with other studies in the different region of world showed that the results are in the range of other researchers. Students' academic performance and well-being are impacted by classroom anxiety stemming from academic pressure and evaluation anxiety, underscoring the vital need for supportive learning settings (17). In terms of demographics variables 45% of participants aged between 18 to 22 years, and 32.14% aged between 23 to 27 years (18). The ratio of gender in current study was 35.72% male 64.28% female Comparatively in a study association of anxiety established with gender 69.7% female reported anxiety(19). About the participants' year of education, 57.14% are in their first year, and 15.71% are in their second year. Third-year students make up 17.86%, while fourth-year students make up 9.29%. 57.14% of the total study participants live in hostels, making up the bulk of the population. Dissimilarly in Rayani DF study about one-third of the study population was represented by the two academic years (the third and the fourth). Over half of the participants had two to four siblings, and the majority (94.7%) lived with their families that is more than the current study (20). In this study 20.72% of the participants report normal range of anxiety, surprisingly in a study conducted in USA 80.4% Of the students report moderate level of anxiety which is higher than the current study (21). In our study 28.57% of participants shows mild to moderate degree of anxiety and alarmingly 42.86% of students report severe degree of anxiety in contrary a study conducted in Nepal on nursing students anxiety level reports only 3.26% during covid 19 outbreak moreover soothingly only 7.85% of the participants reports extreme degree of anxiety level while a study accompanied in Kolkata showed higher level of anxiety 56.59% in nursing students (22).

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, anxiety levels among nursing students in the classroom range from moderate to severe, this has an impact on both their academic performance and mental health. Larger-scale research is still required, and interventional studies must be carried out in the future.

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